
Final report

Bando young researcher

Project title

Advancing patient-centric medical devices for personalized care based on biofeedback

Principal Investigator: Alessandro Luchetti (University of Trento)

Team: Damiano Fruet, Eugenia Spessot, Yiming Dong.

Executive Summary

This report summarizes the scientific, technical, and financial outcomes of the Young Researchers (YR) project “*Advancing patient-centric medical devices for personalized care based on biofeedback*”. The project addresses the need for next-generation assistive and rehabilitative medical devices that go beyond purely mechanical support by integrating physiological biofeedback, advanced sensing, and intelligent control strategies.

The project pursued a multi-scale and multidisciplinary approach. At the **body scale**, a robotic collaborative walker was developed and enhanced to act as an *empathic assistive device*, capable of detecting user intention, monitoring psychophysiological state, and adapting its behavior accordingly. At the **tissue scale**, the project envisioned the development of muscle-on-chip technologies to provide fine-grained physiological insights and capable of measuring physiological parameters relevant for the control of electronic systems.

Key outcomes include: (i) the mechanical and electronic redesign of a robotic walker with multi-modal force sensing, (ii) integration of wearable physiological monitoring (Equival EQ02), (iii) development of real-time algorithms for stress and fatigue estimation, (iv) implementation of a modular multisensorial control software infrastructure, and (v) a shared augmented reality (AR) interface enabling caregiver supervision and empathic interaction. (vi) a scaffolding material for muscle cells allowing for the physiological contraction and the detection of physiological signals *in vitro*. The project results demonstrate the feasibility and relevance of patient-centric, biofeedback-driven assistive devices for rehabilitation and mobility support. Potential integration of technologies at different length scales could open to opportunities for the smart control of devices.

Introduction

Background and Motivation

Medical devices play a crucial role in modern healthcare, supporting diagnosis, therapy, monitoring, and daily living activities. In the context of mobility impairments and neuromuscular disorders, assistive devices such as walkers are widely adopted, yet often remain passive tools that react only to mechanical interaction. This limitation reduces adaptability, user acceptance, and long-term effectiveness.

Recent advances in robotics, wearable sensing, and augmented reality open new opportunities for *patient-centric medical devices* that can interpret not only physical interaction but also the physiological and emotional state of the user. Monitoring stress,

fatigue, and intention enables a shift from reactive assistance to proactive, empathic support.

Project Vision

The overarching vision of this project is to advance medical devices towards *personalized, empathic assistance* by integrating biofeedback at multiple levels. In particular, the project aims to:

- Enhance robotic walkers with multi-sensorial interfaces capable of understanding user intention and physiological state.
- Integrate wearable physiological monitoring to assess stress and fatigue during assisted walking.
- Enable intelligent control strategies that adapt assistance based on biofeedback.
- Provide intuitive tools for caregivers through remote and augmented reality interfaces.

State of the Art

Robotic walkers have evolved significantly in recent years, incorporating shared control, admittance and impedance control strategies, and distributed force sensing to enhance stability and human–robot collaboration (Ye et al., 2018; Itadera & Cheng, 2022; Jimenez et al., 2023). Previous studies demonstrated that tuning virtual inertia, damping, and stiffness parameters can improve perceived safety and walking comfort, particularly in rehabilitation contexts (Aguirre-Ollinger & Yu, 2021).

Despite these advances, most existing systems still present important limitations. **First**, empathic awareness is largely missing: physiological and affective states such as stress, fatigue, or cognitive load are rarely integrated into the control loop, even though they strongly influence gait performance and user acceptance (Garau et al., 2022; Fruet et al., 2023). **Second**, personalization remains limited, as assistance parameters are often predefined or manually tuned by clinicians rather than dynamically adapted to the user's evolving condition (Costa et al., 2024). **Third**, the integration of immersive interfaces is still immature: Virtual or Augmented Reality solutions are typically decoupled from the mechanical and haptic behavior of the walker, resulting in limited coherence between visual feedback and physical interaction (Loureiro et al., 2024).

More recent approaches have begun exploring the integration of AR with assistive walking devices to improve engagement and motivation, while preserving awareness of

the real environment (Luchetti et al., 2020; De Cecco et al., 2023). However, these systems often lack a tight coupling between impedance-based control, multisensorial force feedback, and the user's physiological state.

At the microscale and tissue scale, organ-on-a-chip technologies are used to culture human cells that mimic the structure and function of muscles (i.e., **muscle-on-chip**), to study physiological responses in a more accurate and controlled manner. To exploit this, biomaterials enabling cells contractile materials are required to monitor the function of the contractility in real-time to observe in vitro muscle contraction and function (e.g., electrophysiology used as a biofeedback control system for a robotic assistive/rehabilitative walker).

The present project builds upon and extends the state of the art by combining **torque-based impedance-controlled robotic walking assistance**, **wearable physiological sensing**, and **shared Augmented Reality interfaces** into a unified framework. By explicitly accounting for user biofeedback and intention, the proposed system enables a holistic and empathic rehabilitation paradigm, overcoming key limitations of existing robotic walkers (De Cecco et al., 2025). Furthermore, future extensions of this framework may leverage muscle-on-chip platforms as bio-hybrid testbeds to investigate neuromuscular responses and validate adaptive control strategies under controlled physiological conditions.

Project Objectives

The project objectives, consistent with the original YR proposal, are summarized below.

Scientific and Technological Objectives

- Develop an advanced robotic collaborative walker capable of safe, adaptive, and personalized assistance.
- Integrate multi-axis force sensing to detect user intention and interaction forces.
- Monitor physiological signals related to stress and fatigue using wearable sensors.
- Design real-time algorithms for physiological state estimation.
- Implement a multisensorial, modular control software architecture.
- Enable shared control and supervision through tablet-based and AR interfaces.
- Develop and characterize an elastic precision matrix including natural biomaterials to support differentiation and contraction of myocytes.
- Test mechanical properties and inclusion of human myocytes within the matrix.

Expected Impact

- Improved quality of assistance and rehabilitation outcomes.
- Increased user acceptance through empathic behavior.
- Enhanced caregiver awareness and control.
- A scalable technological platform for future clinical and industrial developments.
- Develop a customized microfluidic chip to include hydrogels and assess myocytes profile of healthy vs diseased cells. Integration of biologically relevant signals from Muscle-on-chip.

System Overview: The Empathic Robotic Walker

Mechanical Design and Kinematics

The robotic collaborative walker features an enveloping and protective mechanical structure, designed to support users of different heights and physical conditions. The walker is height-adjustable and includes multiple connection points for auxiliary aids, such as forearm supports and lateral handles.

A key design advancement introduced in this project concerns the *user support configuration*. In addition to traditional forearm supports, a new ergonomic design was developed allowing the user to rely on lateral graspable handles (Figure 1). This configuration enables alternative walking modalities, including a 180° rotated user orientation, increasing flexibility and usability.

Figure 1 - Walker mechanics: motorized wheels with integrated encoders, drives, logic unit, force sensors under the armrests and and a detailed view highlights the custom-designed lateral handles.

The walker employs a differential-drive kinematic configuration, enabling non-redundant control of planar motion. Two direct-drive motors with integrated encoders are torque-controlled, allowing precise implementation of impedance-based assistance strategies.

Force and Interaction Sensing

To capture user intention and interaction forces, the walker integrates:

- Two triaxial load cells positioned beneath the forearm supports to measure three-dimensional interaction forces.
- Additional force sensors embedded in the lateral handles to detect upper-limb interaction forces.
- Monoaxial load cells with elastic tips integrated into the haptic interface connected to the user's pelvis.

These sensors measure forces along multiple axes, enabling the system to infer the direction and magnitude of the user's intended movement. The force data serve as primary inputs for the impedance control algorithms.

The mechanical redesign and prototyping activities, including CAD design, 3D printing, and mechanical manufacturing, were supported by the **ProM Facility** (<https://promfacility.eu>), which contributed to optimizing ergonomics and manufacturability.

Wearable Physiological Monitoring: The Empathic Interface

Physiological Sensing Platform

To assess the physiological state of the user during assisted walking, the project integrated the Equival EQ02 Lifemonitor, a certified medical-grade wearable system. The device acquires:

- Two-lead electrocardiogram (ECG).
- Photoplethysmogram (PPG).
- Respiratory signal via chest-worn belt.
- Body movement and posture via an inertial measurement unit (IMU).

ECG and PPG signals are sampled at 256 Hz, respiration at 25.6 Hz, and IMU data at 256 Hz. All signals are time-synchronized and streamed in real time to a dedicated processing unit via Bluetooth.

Physiological Feature Extraction

Real-time algorithms were developed to extract informative features from physiological signals:

- **ECG:** After band-pass filtering (0.1–120 Hz), R-peaks are detected using the Pan–Tompkins algorithm (Pan & Tompkins, 2007). Heart rate variability (HRV) features such as mean RR, standard deviation, and RMSSD are computed.
- **PPG:** Filtered in the 0.05–30 Hz band, with detection of systolic and diastolic peaks. Timing, amplitude, skewness, and kurtosis features are extracted.
- **Respiration:** Low- and high-pass filtering (0.01–5 Hz) followed by extraction of inspiration/expiration times and areas.

Figure 2 - Equivital EQ02 Life Monitor sensor: (a) belt, (b) SEM, and (c) positioning. [Image reproduced from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24175479>]

Physiological State Classification

All extracted features are combined and fed into a k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) classifier, selected for its simplicity, computational efficiency, and robustness in real-time applications. The classifier estimates the user's physiological status, providing indicators of stress and fatigue that are used to modulate walker behavior.

Control Software and Multisensorial Integration

Motor Control and Impedance Strategy

The walker implements torque-based impedance control, allowing the system to render virtual inertia, friction, and elastic behaviors. This enables smooth, natural interaction and safe collaboration between human and robot.

The control framework supports:

- Direct speed/torque control (for testing and manual operation).

- Trajectory-following based on predefined waypoints or clothoids.
- Shared and remote-control modes.

Multisensorial Software Architecture

A modular software infrastructure was developed to integrate motors, encoders, force sensors, physiological sensors, and external interfaces. Communication between system components is based on the MQTT protocol, enabling reliable and scalable data exchange.

The software architecture includes watchdog mechanisms to ensure safety: in the absence of valid inputs within predefined time windows, the robot autonomously stops.

External Engineering Contribution

An external engineering collaborator contributed significantly to the development of:

- Motor driver software with serial communication.
- MQTT-based communication framework.
- Sensor acquisition infrastructure (including load cells).
- Linux-based control PC configuration.

The resulting system is fully modular and built on open-source operating systems and libraries, ensuring long-term maintainability and extensibility.

7. Caregiver Interface and Augmented Reality

Tablet-Based Remote Interface

A tablet interface was developed to allow caregivers to:

- Select operating modes, Figure 3.
- Configure walker control parameters, Figure 4.
- Monitor real-time physiological parameters, Figure 5.

This interface provides an intuitive and accessible tool for clinical supervision.

Figure 3 - App interface: mode selection

Figure 4 - App interface: configuration of walker impedance control parameters.

Figure 5 – App interface: real-time monitoring of physiological parameters during path-following task

Shared Augmented Reality Control

Beyond traditional interfaces, the project explored shared AR interaction. Caregivers can visualize user performance and environmental context, and collaboratively influence walker behavior. AR enhances engagement while preserving awareness of the real environment, unlike fully immersive VR solutions.

Experimental Observations and Limitations

During the project, the complete empathic walking-assistance framework was experimentally evaluated in laboratory conditions. The system was tested by the research team to assess functional integration, real-time performance, and usability of the combined mechanical, physiological, and software components.

A key design advancement introduced in this project concerns the **user support configuration**. In addition to traditional forearm supports, a new ergonomic solution based on **lateral graspable handles** was developed and experimentally tested. This configuration enables the user to rely on hand-held supports rather than forearm rests and allows **alternative walking modalities**, including operation with the user **rotated by 180°** with respect to the standard configuration. Preliminary tests confirmed the feasibility of this solution and highlighted increased flexibility in user posture and

interaction with the walker, particularly in scenarios requiring different levels of upper-limb involvement.

The proposed multisensorial framework, combining force-based intention detection with wearable physiological monitoring, was successfully operated in real time. The synchronized acquisition of interaction forces, kinematic data, and physiological parameters enabled continuous estimation of the user's state during assisted walking. The **tablet-based caregiver interface**, providing real-time visualization of both mechanical and physiological indicators, was tested and received **positive qualitative feedback from expert users and clinical professionals**, who identified it as a valuable tool for supporting supervision and decision-making during rehabilitation activities.

From a mechanical perspective, the integration of **omnidirectional wheels** was investigated to mitigate singularities and stalling phenomena occurring during rotations of the walker's free front wheels, Figure 6. While this solution improved maneuverability in certain conditions, experimental observations revealed **non-smooth behavior at low speeds**, indicating the need for further optimization of both mechanical design and low-speed control strategies prior to deployment in real-world clinical environments.

Figure 6 - Installation of omni-directional wheels on the walker

9. Prototyping a Muscle-on-Chip

The development of contractile *in vitro* systems able to mimic human electrophysiology is challenging. In this project, elastic composite hydrogels were engineered to mimic both biochemical and mechanical properties using the myocardium as a validator (Paz-Artigas et al., 2023). Hydrogels were engineered to mimic cardiac features by incorporating components able to mimic contractility of human tissues, namely collagen, gelatin, alginate and hyaluronic acid. Testing of developed hydrogels was performed to ensure elasticity compatible with contraction and human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) were differentiated to cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs) and used to assess hydrogel cytocompatibility, as well as testing their ability to support cell adhesion, survival, and hiPSC-CMs synchronous beating.

Hydrogels: formulation and mechanical testing

Precision matrix (polymeric network with controlled mechanical features) that supports the contractile activity of muscle tissue within the chip model was obtained as composite hydrogels obtained mixing alginate, oxidized alginate, and collagen, crosslinked via CaCl_2 solution and Schiff's base reaction. In specific, hydrogels were designed to mimic myocardium mechanical properties, based on our previous knowledge. Hydrogels stability was assessed using swelling testing, whereas rheology, and nanoindentation tests were used to analyze mechanical properties. Stock solutions of 2% (w/v) sodium alginate (A0, KIMICA ALGIN IL-6G, Japan) and oxidized alginate with a target oxidation degree of 5% (OA5) were separately prepared in HEPES-Buffered Saline (G2225, ChemCruz, USA). A0 was dissolved at room temperature overnight, while OA5 required approx. 1 hour. Both solutions were sterile-filtered through 0.22 μm PES membranes prior to use. Type I bovine collagen (TeloCol[®]-6, Advanced BioMatrix, USA) was diluted to 3 mg/mL ("Col-3") or 1.5 mg/mL ("Col-15").

Equal volumes of A0 and OA5 stock solutions were mixed on ice to form the "mixed solution," which was then combined with the diluted collagen and neutralization solution according to the target collagen concentration. All mixing steps were performed on ice to prevent premature collagen fibrillogenesis. The mixture was homogenized by repeated pipetting until uniform and free of air bubbles, then dispensed into molds (1 mL for rheology; 200 μL for nanoindentation) and incubated at 37 °C for 1 h to allow collagen fibrillogenesis and covalent Schiff base formation between OA5 aldehyde and collagen amine groups.

Hydrogels were ionically crosslinked by immersion in CaCl_2 solutions (prepared from solid calcium chloride dihydrate, 208290, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) at room temperature for 10

min, with gentle detachment to ensure full contact. Hydrogels were incubated in HBS at 37 °C overnight to assess their stability in water-like environment (Swelling tests), confirming their stability as expected (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Swelling ratio of alginate-collage hydrogels crosslinked with diffred CaCl₂ concentrations (N=1, n=5).

The viscoelastic properties of the hydrogels were comprehensively quantified using a Discovery HR-2 Rheometer (TA Instruments, USA) equipped with a 25mm parallel plate Peltier geometry (Perin et al., 2023). All tests were performed isothermally at 25 °C under a constant pre-load axial force of 0.1 N to ensure stable contact between the sample and the geometries. Initially, oscillatory strain sweep tests were conducted to determine the Linear Viscoelastic Region (LVR), where the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') were continuously measured over a strain range of 0.1% to 100% at a fixed frequency of 1 Hz. Subsequently, a single transient creep and recovery test was executed to evaluate the material's time-dependent deformation under a fixed stress. A constant shear stress of 20.0 Pa was applied for a creep time of 900.0 s; this stress was then instantaneously removed for a recovery time of 900.0 s, during which the strain recovery was monitored. Finally, the material's recovery behavior was assessed through a three-stage oscillatory time sweep under the same conditions (25 °C, 1 Hz): the initial viscoelastic response was established by applying a low strain of 1% (within the LVR) for 60 s; the strain was then increased to 100% for 60 s; and the strain was immediately reduced back to 1% and

monitored for 300 s to track the structural changes. Both G' and G'' were continuously recorded throughout all three stages.

Figure 8 – Storage modulus (G') of alginate-collagen hydrogels obtained using rheological tests.

To measure the elastic moduli (E) of the hydrogels, a Bioindenter™ UNHT 3 Bio (Anton Paar GmbH, Anton Paar Graz, Austria) equipped with a ruby spherical probe (diameter of $1000 \mu\text{m}$, $\nu_i = 0.07$, $E_i = 1141 \text{ GPa}$) was used. The tests were performed with linear loading and unloading rate 0.300 mN/min and a pause of 5.0 s was applied to ensure that the maximum load (0.10 mN) was achieved. The contact stiffness threshold was set at $0.5 \mu\text{N}/\mu\text{m}$. For each sample, 8 points were tested.

Figure 9 - Examples of force-displacement nanoindentation curves of alginate-collagen hydrogels; each sample was indented in 8 different points.

Tested hydrogels shown mechanical properties compatible with healthy and fibrotic cardiac tissue (Benech et al., 2022). In specific, rheological (Figure 8) and nanoindentation (Figure 9) tests highlight that viscoelastic properties of cardio-hydrogels are controlled by CaCl_2 and collagen concentrations, independently.

Hydrogels and human cells: assessing contraction

Human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) were differentiated to cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs) following an optimized protocol (Niro et al., 2024) and the cytocompatibility of hydrogels was assessed *in vitro* models as first step towards muscle-on-chip development (as shown in Figure 7). Biological results confirm hiPSCs-CMs adhesion, survival, and contractility, as confirmed by brightfield microscopy and immunofluorescence staining. The developed models successfully replicated cardiac contractile properties, supporting their use as functional *in vitro* contractile models (Figure 8).

Figure 10 - Representation of a typical *in vitro* model to assess contraction of cells (top) enabled by the alginate-collagen hydrogels (bottom). This model was designed to evaluate hiPSC-CM beating ability in different hydrogels.

Figure 11 - Brightfield microscope images of hiPSCs-CMs cultured on top of alginate-collagen hydrogels with A) soft (CaCl_2 0.1 M), B) medium (CaCl_2 0.2 M) and C) stiff elastic modulus (CaCl_2 0.3 M).

Printability of hydrogels and human cells: towards muscle-on-chip

Manufacturing of 3D structures on chip enables to better correlate with physiological responses, acquired with microelectrodes. The use of different hydrogels also enables better understanding of differences between healthy and diseased myocytes. Note that due to time constraints, it was not possible to integrate the materials within the chip and to test the muscle-on-chip as initially envisioned. Preliminary experiments to detect myocytes contractility were performed using selected alginate-collagen hydrogels in CUORE device (in collaboration with King's College London, Figure 12), as prototype of 3D contractile *in vitro* models and measuring a contractile force of approx. 0.1 mN in each tested sample. Future integration of sensing systems (e.g., microelectrodes) could provide physiologically relevant signals to be integrated in the biofeedback framework.

Figure 12 – Myocytes cultured on hydrogels in the CUORE system to measure contractile force.

10. Dissemination of Results

The dissemination of the project results was carried out through a combination of international scientific conferences, public engagement initiatives, and international research collaboration.

10.1 International Scientific Dissemination

The main scientific outcomes of the project were disseminated at the **2025 IEEE International Conference on Metrology for eXtended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXRINE 2025)**, held in Ancona, Italy, from **22 to 24 October**

2025. The paper entitled “*Robotic Collaborative Walker with Impedance Control and Augmented Reality for Assisted Walking and User Empowerment*” was presented orally by the Principal Investigator.

Authors: M. De Cecco, G. Nollo, A. Luchetti, M. Bonetto, D. Fruet, M. Irtaza, Md M. Rahman, R. Shigeto, I. Butaslac.

Affiliations: (1) Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Trento (Italy); (2) Nara Institute of Science and Technology (Japan).

This contribution allowed the project to reach an international audience spanning metrology, robotics, extended reality, and biomedical engineering, fostering discussion on empathic assistive devices and biofeedback-driven rehabilitation systems.

Another scientific outcome was presented at the **34th Annual Conference of the European Society for Biomaterials (ESB 2025)**, held in Turin, Italy, from the **7th to the 11th September 2025**. The paper “*Design and characterization of functional biopolymers for cardiac in vitro models*” was presented orally.

Authors: Eugenia Spessot 1, Anna Rossi Lanzoni 1, Cristina Mazzotti 2, Alessia Metallo 2, Stefania Pagliari 2, Giancarlo Forte 2, Annalisa Tirella 1

Affiliations (1) University of Trento, Italy; (2) King’s College London, UK

This contribution allowed the project to reach an international audience spanning material scientists, biologists and biomedical engineers, fostering discussion on the ability of the systems to culture muscle cells and measuring the contractile events.

10.2 Public Engagement and Citizen-Oriented Dissemination

In addition to scientific dissemination, the project was selected by the **Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Trento** for presentation during the **European Researchers’ Night 2025 (26 September 2025)**. The demonstrator “*Robotic Collaborative Walker*” was showcased at the **MUSE – Museo delle Scienze (Trento)**, one of the main venues for public science communication in the region.

This event enabled direct interaction with a broad audience, including citizens, students, and families, increasing awareness of assistive robotics and augmented reality technologies applied to healthcare. The demonstrator emphasized the societal relevance of patient-centric and empathic medical devices, aligning the project with iNEST cross-cutting activities on citizen engagement and dissemination.

10.3 International Research Collaboration and Mobility

As part of the dissemination and promotion of the project results, an international research visit was carried out at the **Nara Institute of Science and Technology (NAIST), Japan, from 1 February 2025 to 28 February 2025**, hosted by the laboratory of **Prof. Hirokazu Kato**, a pioneer and internationally recognized authority in Augmented Reality.

This visit strengthened the long-standing collaboration between NAIST and the **MiroLab – Measurements, Instrumentation, and Robotics Laboratory**, directed by Prof. De Cecco. During the stay, project results were presented and discussed with international researchers, fostering knowledge exchange on augmented reality, human–robot interaction, and assistive technologies. The visit contributed to increasing the international visibility of the project and laid the groundwork for future joint research initiatives and publications.

11. Budget and Resource Utilization

Project funds were primarily allocated to:

- Procurement of triaxial load cells.
- Procurement of omnidirectional wheels
- Mechanical redesign and prototyping of the walker (CAD, 3D printing, machining).
- Procurement of a wearable physiological monitoring system (Equival EQ02).
- Procurement of a tablet to be used as a caregiver remote interface
- Engineering support for multisensorial control software.
- Polymers (Methacrylated gelatin (GelMA), Hyaluronic Acid, Collagen) to prepare hydrogels to support muscle cells growth
- Capillary Pipette tips for managing viscous fluids to manufacture hydrogels with high precision.
- Chemicals and reagents to control the formation of hydrogels and testing.

All expenditures directly supported the scientific and technological advancement of the YR project.

Conclusions and Future Work

This project successfully demonstrated a patient-centric, empathic approach to assistive robotics by integrating mechanical interaction, physiological monitoring, and intelligent

control. The robotic walker evolved from a passive aid into an adaptive system capable of understanding and responding to the user's physical and physiological state.

Future work will focus on:

- Completing and validating the muscle-on-chip integration.
- Extended clinical trials with diverse user populations.
- Refinement of low-speed omnidirectional mobility.
- Advanced machine learning methods for personalized biofeedback.

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